

Happiness in times of change:

Friluftsliv on Svalbard

Research report to the Svalbards Miljøvernfond

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1. Background and introduction

1.1. Aim and focus of the project

Svalbard's nature is fundamentally changing due to global climate change. Simultaneously, the popularity of the archipelago as an exotic travel destination is increasing due to an intentional economic restructuring from coal to tourism. This is advocated as part of Svalbard's "green transition" towards a carbon-free economy but presents environmental and social challenges of its own. According to the Norwegian government, Svalbard is supposed to be one of the world's best-managed wilderness areas, and environmental regulations are currently being revised and strengthened. The common imaginary of the Svalbard nature is thus one of an empty wilderness, pristine, harsh, and desolate, that is being threatened by climate change and thus must be protected (Brode-Roger 2020). What is often overlooked in such portrayals of the Svalbard nature is the role it plays for the people living on the archipelago, their life-projects, and wellbeing. This aim of this project is to document and analyze current outdoor-practices (*friluftsliv*) among Svalbard residents, understand the motivations and aspirational dimensions behind outdoor activities in Svalbard's wilderness areas, and analyze the impact of an expanding tourism industry, increased regulations, and climate change on local ways of living, through ethnographic fieldwork, film, photography, and interviews.

Environmental policies are determining Svalbard inhabitants' possibilities to access and use the natural environment on the archipelago. However, these political decisions almost exclusively rely on research from the natural sciences and rarely consider the human dimension. Alongside the recent turn towards the Anthropocene discourse in social sciences and politics, there risk is that the perspectives, needs, and desires of local communities and the broader public is given less importance, as has been the case in the establishment of protected areas in other parts of the world (West & Brockington 2006). This project aims to highlight the sociocultural importance of the Svalbardian landscape in collective and individual life-projects by examining the way people use the outdoors on Svalbard, and the values and meanings attributed to these practices as well as the environment. It further examines the tensions and dilemmas that arise when these practices and values are challenged by economic and political claims to the Svalbard wilderness.

1.2. Research questions

The research is guided by the following research questions:

- How do people practice *friluftsliv* (life in the outdoors) on Svalbard?
- How do people perceive and experience the landscape on Svalbard?
- Which conflicts arise in the intersection of different interests and perspectives—experiential, economic, political—on the natural landscape?
- How are traditional practices related to the pursuit of the good life challenged and transformed by economic and political developments?

We are thus interested in the *meanings of friluftsliv* to people on Svalbard (inhabitants and visitors), how Svalbard's landscape is *valued* across different dimensions, and in the different outdoor *practices* people on Svalbard rely on in order to strengthen a sense of well-being and belonging articulated through the concept of *bolyst* (lit. 'desire to dwell'). While the focus is on peoples' lived experiences, we examine these in their sociocultural context, with a focus on the expanding tourist industry and increasing environmental regulations.

1.3. Conceptual framework: Dilemmas of the empty wilderness

Working with the camera and photography made us attuned to how the landscape on Svalbard often is represented, imagined, and promoted as *empty* of people. The idea of the empty landscape is very much rooted in Western, modern ideas of the separation of nature and culture, of humans and the environment. While such dichotomous thinking is increasingly challenged, this idea forms the basis of both the capitalist exploitation of nature (nature as resource to be extracted, man as the master of nature) as well as of Western conservation practices (man as the protector and steward of nature). Through the research process, we became interested in understanding how the idea of the empty Svalbard landscape is actualized across different dimensions. We do not mean to say that the Svalbardian landscape is, in reality, empty (of people or human traces) but rather, we are interested in how a notion of emptiness is actualized or mobilized across different dimensions, and how emptiness can act as a concept that highlight the interconnections between different practices relating to the "wilderness" landscape.

We structure our analysis around three dimensions in which the idea of the empty landscape is actualized: the experiential, the economic, and the political. The **experiential** or phenomenological dimension refers to peoples' experience of the landscape. We describe how emptiness is actualized in peoples' search for adventure, their experience of joy in the outdoors, and especially their desire to roam across a vast and open landscape, showing how outdoor practices are both entangled with collective and individual identity projects as well as pursuits of existential meaning and joy. These practices are rooted in a romantic tradition that understands nature as a source of meaning, authenticity, and belonging in a disenchanted and alienating modern world. The empty landscape emerges as a space for spiritual healing, existential meaning, expressing, and belonging, expressing a romantic desire to "reconnect" in what Hartmut Rosa (2019) describes as a *resonant* way with the world.

Next, we explore how the fantasy of the empty landscape as a place to reconnect with the world is transformed into a product that can be sold. The **economic dimension** thus refers to the commodification of "wilderness" and "empty" landscape through tourism. However, while the transformation of "wilderness experiences" into objects for elite consumption is legitimized through a discourse of sustainability (economic and environmental), it is far from an innocuous practice. It produces environmental impacts as well as social tensions (related to democratic access) and transforms traditional ways of relating to the landscape.

Finally, we examine national conservation policies that seek to maintain and produce a presumably empty landscape (**political dimension**). Svalbard's special legal status as an area regulated through the Svalbard treaty and its largely transient population means that the dynamics and tensions between local and national political decision-making is different from those on mainland Norway, challenging traditional Norwegian understandings of local democracy. Thus, customary rights such as *allemannsretten* (the right to roam), which is central to outdoor practices on mainland Norway, are configured differently on Svalbard, producing further tensions between local communities and state on the archipelago.

On the basis of this conceptual framework we will discuss what happens when people's pursuit of the good life in the outdoors is challenged by increasing tourism and environmental regulations that seek to restrict public access to the outdoors, and to what extent different practices challenge or reproduce the mechanistic and instrumental relations to the landscape

that are often seen at the center of modern ways of relating to the world. We analyze the tensions and collusion between local pursuits of the good life through engagement with nature, the growth of tourism and emphasis on Svalbard as an elite destination, and the new environmental regulation implemented in recent policy-plans. We consider the usefulness of understanding the Svalbardian wilderness as a common in the context of an ongoing process of territorial reordering negotiated by state, market, and the public. How are changing conditions in the way that we engage with and interact with the natural landscape affecting contemporary pursuits of happiness and the good life in Svalbard?

2. Methods: Ethnographic fieldwork and visual methods

The project is based on ethnographic fieldwork in Longyearbyen between 2019 and 2022. During our field visits in Longyearbyen we participated in a broad variety of outdoor activities, ranging from excursions with students from the local high-school, eco-tourist sailing expeditions, snow-mobile expeditions with local residents, cabin trips, hunting trips, and day-trips in the proximity of Longyearbyen. We recorded 23 qualitative interviews and engaged in multiple informal conversations with a broad range of people, including long-term Norwegian residents, seasonal workers from different countries, scientists, tour operators, nature guides, and polar expeditioners. The data obtained from interviews and participant observation was complemented with white papers, policy proposals, policy consultation comments (*høringsuttalelser*), as well as local and national news. We followed the local debate closely between our field visits by keeping in touch with research participants, reading the local newspaper *Svalbardposten*, and discussions in *Facebook*-groups. Documentary filmmaker Siri Bråtveit accompanied the research process and is working on an independent film-project partly funded by Sørnorsk Filmsenter. In addition, we have used photography as a method to document and communicate our findings. In December 2021 we exposed some of these pictures at 2Walls Studio in Barcelona and in May 2022 we organized a photographic exposition at the public library in Longyearbyen at the public presentation of our preliminary findings. We are also in the process of publishing a photographic essay in an edited volume on nature in the Nordic countries.

Photo: Tomas Salem

3. Findings and results

Outdoor life—*friluftsliv*—on Svalbard has several distinct characteristics. Longyearbyen is an international and cosmopolitan community. The large distances and absence of roads makes alternative motorized transport (snowmobiles and boats) crucial for the practice of outdoor life. The environmental and climatic conditions are harsh, which in combination with the remoteness of the place and the absence of cell-phone coverage outside of the settlements makes most ventures into nature an extreme and expedition-like experience. Current outdoor practices can be understood as a continuation of Svalbard’s history as a place for polar exploration and tourism, both dating back to the 19th century.

3.1. The experiential dimension: Meanings and values connected to outdoor life on Svalbard

A main aim of our study has been to examine what outdoor life on Svalbard means for the people who practice it. Recurring themes in our interviews were the importance of finding peace and stillness, roaming the vast and empty landscape, exploring the wilderness, the

history and cultural heritage of the islands seen in the human traces that are scattered across the islands, the social dimension of life in the outdoors, having fun, self-optimizing and feelings of achievement. In the following, we will shortly describe some of the main categories that emerged through the interviews.

3.1.1. The importance of life in the outdoors for people's desire to live on Svalbard

Many come to Svalbard in pursuit of the romantic allure of wilderness adventure. The prospect of living and working with easy access to the archipelago's spectacular landscape and the many possibilities for practicing outdoor life is attracting people to the archipelago and a main motivation for staying on Svalbard.

There is a lot of skepticism towards the new proposed regulations [environmental regulations that restrict access to parts of the Svalbard nature], can you talk a bit about that?

Yes, there is a skepticism, or you can call it a fear for what will happen to our possibilities to practice *friluftsliv* on Svalbard. So, one experiences that it kind of boils down to *bolyst* [the desire to dwell] and quality of life. We live here because we want to go on trips. The job is good to have because you make money, but, if you exaggerate a bit, you can say that we live here because we want to be out in the mountains, we want to go out there, we don't want to sit here in Longyearbyen. And if these possibilities to practice *friluftsliv* are being taken away from us the whole fundament for living here disappears. All that is out there is the reason why we live here, for many of us. It is the adventure of coming here and experiencing Svalbard that attracts us, it is not the possibility to sit in a pub in Longyearbyen. (Interview with male Norwegian long-term resident of Svalbard, 54 years, May 2020)

In this quote, a long-term Norwegian resident of Svalbard expresses that access to nature and the possibility to practice outdoor life constitutes a main factor for his desire to live (*bolyst*) on Svalbard, and by referring to "we" he indicates that this is a shared sense among many residents, which we confirmed through several other interviews, conversations, and observations. The importance of different outdoor practices in Svalbard pervades individual and collective identities and life-projects, especially among western subjects. There is a strong, shared sense that one of the main reasons for living on the island is the spectacular landscape and environment of the islands.

3.1.2. The history of polar exploration and the idealization of the polar hero

What was it with the nature here that attracted you?

I was interested in the outdoors, before I came, in hunting and fishing and boat and fjords and the mountains, the ordinary *friluftsliv*, for someone from Finnmark, with scooter and everything that comes with that. So, it was kind of, Svalbard has a mystery about it, that makes you want to experience it, it is the trapping tradition and old cabins and the history and the cultural heritage and everything that you want to experience, on the whole archipelago. And that is attractive. (*Interview with male long-term resident of Svalbard, 47 years, May 2020*)

As expressed in this quote, the history of hunting, trapping and polar exploration are of great importance for the practice of outdoor life on Svalbard. The history of the archipelago inspires people, and the ethos of exploration is played out in expeditions, scientific pursuits, and tourism referencing the history of the islands. Material remnants of the past, such as old trappers' cabins, stand as reminders of this history that can be reenacted by the modern adventurer. Relatedly, the ideal of the rugged and self-reliant polar explorer figures prominently in the modern adventurers' accounts of what attracted them to Svalbard, where, indeed, everyone can be an explorer, as one of our research participants told us during a trip to Northern Spitsbergen told us. In conversations, the self-sufficiency and independence required by the remote and harsh conditions were often described as a virtue, and resilience, as the ability to survive and thrive in the extreme and hostile Svalbardian landscape, was highly valued by practitioners of outdoor life as well as by the local community at large.

Even if the adventurer that travels to far-away places figure prominently in many of our interlocutors' ideas of what constitutes a good life on Svalbard, there is also a strong focus on simpler activities in the immediate surroundings of Longyearbyen. This is typical of the outdoor culture of mainland Norway and is often referred to as *nærfriluftslivet*. As was repeatedly emphasized in interviews, one does not have to go far in order to experience Svalbard's landscape, and for many, going to remote and unknown locations is not an aspiration. However, even hiking up to the peaks surrounding town requires gear and knowledge about the Svalbard environment.

Photo: Tomas Salem

3.1.3. Mobility and the freedom to roam

Connected to the ethos of exploration, the freedom to roam the archipelago is understood by many of our interlocutors as a crucial aspect of leading a fulfilling life on Svalbard. Unrestricted mobility and the possibility to go far are highly valued, and strongly associated with *bolyst* by many inhabitants.

So, when it comes to mobility, one thing is to go on these weekend trips. But then you have this certainty, you have this possibility to go somewhere. And maybe you make the trip in twenty years on Svalbard, to go that cabin or that place, this dream to go there and you know that you have the possibility to do so, legally [laughs], to know that you have the possibility to go far, far away out into the unknown. If you put like a fictional fence around town here, five miles in each direction and that's it, then you lose this possibility, you lose a bit of the dream. The dream to go to Texas Bar, on scooter, I have done that. Or the dream of driving to Sørkapp, I haven't done that. That dream is very strong, and it is to kind of know that you can, if I want, and if the weather is good and everything lines up, maybe next year, maybe next weekend, who knows. This is very important, this dream trip, that maybe can be done. And it is important that that does possibility is not cut off, to say that it can never happen, because then you lose a bit of the motivation, I think. The best trips are the ones that you plan sitting

at the pub, at midnight. Those are the most fun trips. Maybe they never happen, but it is the possibility that is there. (*Interview with male, long-term inhabitant of Svalbard, in his fifties, February 2020*)

In this quote, the allure of the unregulated and unfenced landscape, and the freedom that is associated with it, comes to the fore. Indeed, Svalbard is sometimes described as a “Wild West” and frontier of civilization—a vast, unregulated landscape that invites adventurers to venture forth “into the unknown” and explore, beyond the confines of conventional society. As remarked in the quote, there is an increasing feeling that this freedom is gradually being lost, a point we will return to below.

Photo: Tomas Salem

3.1.4. The wilderness as a social space for belonging

To many Svalbardians, the wilderness is also a space to cultivate relations of belonging to the local community and landscape. It is dotted with personal and collective memories, and engaging with the landscape contributes to the construction of a shared identity and sense of belonging. People have emotional ties to specific locations and cabins, and sharing stories from these places helps establish a connection with the local community. The landscape and

life in the outdoors thus become crucial sources of collective as well as individual identity. Some of our interview partners describe intimate relations to the Svalbard landscape. In the following quote, a mother described how it felt moving back to Svalbard with her children after living several years on the mainland:

We noted that [we relaxed] immediately when we came here. It was exactly like coming home. It was like... Oh, here we can breathe. There is something about the lack of time on the mainland. It felt so good to escape. I suddenly got time to take my kids out into nature. [...] [Longyearbyen] has always been a changing community... But one thing doesn't change: the mountains. [...] To me it's a bit like coming home, and it's not because I know so many people here that I depend on, it is the nature that makes me feel more at home here than [on the mainland], really. (*Interview with Norwegian, female, long-term resident of Svalbard, in her forties, May 2021*)

A return to the Svalbard landscape is here conceptualized as a home-coming, expressing the deep sense of belonging to the nature rather than the community in Longyearbyen, which is described as much more transient. Nonetheless, while this woman stressed her belonging to the mountains, love for the Svalbardian nature is a strong identity-marker and produces a sense of belonging to the local community as well.

Photo: Tomas Salem

Relatedly, outdoor life practices, such as hiking, going on cabin trips, or fishing, play a vital role in fostering social connections among individuals. Many of our interview partners emphasize the significance of the social aspect of excursions, considering it to be just as crucial as the experience of the natural landscape. The outdoors constitutes a social arena for various activities such as child-rearing, dating, forming and reaffirming friendships, receiving education, group formation, social integration, and inter-generational and international socialization. In fact, some individuals we have spoken with even regard the outdoors as the public square of Norwegian society, a dimension of the outdoors that became even more apparent during the pandemic. Particularly, cabin trips are central for establishing and maintaining social bonds on Svalbard, similarly to the Norwegian mainland.

3.2. The economic dimension: The commodification of the wilderness

On Svalbard as elsewhere, the allure of the empty, pristine, and untouched wilderness has become turned into a product to be sold and consumed in nature-based tourism (Kotašková 2020). The exponential growth in international tourism that has swept across the world's last remaining wilderness areas with increased intensity in the beginning of the 21st century is strongly felt in Svalbard, where tourism has become the main economic backbone of Longyearbyen in the intended transition from coal extraction into an economically and environmentally sustainable future (Hovelsrud et al. 2021, Saville 2022). The sustainability narrative in Svalbard tourism, however, is increasingly being challenged (Andersen 2022) as the commodification of the natural landscape often runs at odds with environmental concerns and produces social challenges such as a chronic lack of housing and precarious, seasonal labor.

The "destination" today caters to a range of different segments, spanning cruise-ships carrying thousands of passengers, individual travelers on a budget, to a growing luxury segment with tailored trips and fine dining. The exponential growth of Svalbard tourism over the past decades is not just a consequence of large-scale global processes that escape local control, but actively sought by local businesses and supported through state policies and infrastructural developments. While often defended as providing economic sustenance and job-opportunities to the local community, the downside of tourism can be observed in the way it is reshaping people's interactions with the natural environment towards increasingly

commodified relations, the environmental impact and stress it produces, as well as the precarious work-conditions that characterizes the industry when compared to other sectors (such as science, technology, and mining).

Svalbard tourism is mainly nature-based and one of its main products on offer is experiences of the empty Svalbard landscape (Kotašková 2022). However, the increased consumption makes the product less attractive, and people express fear that the wilderness on Svalbard landscape is becoming overcrowded. This is sometime expressed as a paradox (i.e. *friluftsparadokset*), yet it is an expectable outcome of the commodification and consumption of nature. Local discussions about tourism on Svalbard address this and related problems with over-tourism, and many agree that one way out of the dilemma would be to “grow in quality, not in quantity.” The local tourism industry states in its *Masterplan for tourism on Svalbard* that tourists with “high yield, low impact” should be prioritized (Visit Svalbard 2022: 50). In this imaginary, the empty Svalbard landscape is protected against mass tourism and reimagined as a commodity to be sold to wealthy elites. The problem with this line of thinking was expressed by one of our interview partners:

The opportunity to experience Svalbard should not be reserved for the wealthy, this is undemocratic and would also go against *Allemannsretten* [the Norwegian right to roam the landscape]. (*Interview with Norwegian female, long-term resident of Svalbard, in her forties, June 2020*)

Turning Svalbard into an elite destination for luxury tourism might make sense from an economic and environmental point of view but would in effect reserve the possibility of experiencing the islands to wealthy elites (like it has been in the past), where access to one of the world’s last remaining wilderness areas is dependent on economic capabilities. This situates Svalbard within a global trend towards the privatization of nature, whereby access is increasingly regulated through market mechanisms. Framing the problem through the Malthusian idea of overpopulation—i.e. that there are too many people wanting to experience the Svalbard nature shifts attention from the real problem, which is the increasing commodification of the wilderness. Among some of our research participants, the transformation of Svalbard’s wilderness into a space for elite consumption was perceived to go against central Norwegian values, such as equality and the right to roam.

3.3. The political dimension: Makings of the empty wilderness as a geopolitical tool

Norway is bound by the Svalbard Treaty to preserve the archipelago's unique environment. The national environmental regime on Svalbard is now being strengthened and expanded through a series of new rules and regulations, with a general trend towards restricting access to nature for residents of Svalbard, visitors from the mainland, and national as well as international tourists partaking in paid excursions. In the name of environmental protection, the Svalbard landscape is being emptied of people. However, the establishment of new protected areas and new regulations on Svalbard is also part of a geopolitical strategy to demarcate presence and exercise Norwegian sovereignty over the archipelago (Saville 2019). The importance of environmental geopolitics is increasing as coalmining is phased out. By erasing traces of the mining industry and closing off areas to humans, the Norwegian state is marking *presence by human absence* (Ødegaard 2021). Hence, the empty landscape figures as an important category both in imageries of an environmentally responsible Svalbard and in the demarcation of Norwegian presence.

4. Tensions and dilemmas over the “empty” wilderness

Thus, we have observed different engagements with the Svalbard landscape (experiential, economic, and political) which are sometimes colluding and playing into each other, while they at other times are in conflict, producing dilemmas that might not be easy to solve. We have chosen to approach the friction between these perspectives through the notion of *emptiness* as an experience that people pursue, a product that can be sold, and a state of the environment that must be protected.

First, there is a tension between the experiential and political engagements with the Svalbard landscape: between people's desire to access, roam, and be in the landscape on the one hand, and increasing environmental regulations and protected areas on the other. Many research participants expressed concerns that the possibility to practice outdoor activities will be curtailed. Restricted access to nature will likely affect people's wellbeing and experiences of “the good life” on the archipelago, including recreational activities, identity, social relations, belonging and meaningful and resonant ways of relating to the environment. While our focus is on residents of Longyearbyen, the regulations will significantly curtail access to the

outdoors among visitors from the mainland, especially those who do not participate in paid excursions. A main complaint many islanders have against increasing environmental protection and regulations is that their influence on these decisions is negligent and diffculted by bureaucratic processes:

There were so many hearing processes going on at once, and they came so fast, so it was really hard for people to have an overview. [...] We are not being heard, so we lose the motivation for contributing with hearing consultation input. *(Interview with female, Norwegian long-term resident of Svalbard in her fifties, August 2022)*

Many are frustrated with national authorities. These are perceived to making top-down decisions with limited local involvement. The growing discontent with new regulations affects people's desire to stay on Svalbard, with some long-term residents now considering "moving down" to the mainland:

We'll have to see how it develops, but I think it goes very fast and a lot has happened in the past years. We will see. But of course, the key is *friluftslivet*, if that is restricted drastically then I think we all become café-latte men and can sit on a café somewhere on mainland Norway. *(Interview with male Norwegian long-term resident of Svalbard, 54 years, May 2020)*

It should be noted that the opposition to new regulations is pronounced in specific segments of the population, including long-term residents and people who move to Svalbard in search of a wilderness adventure. While these are mainly white, western, middle-class subjects, there are also parts of the population who do not engage in outdoor activities, due to their cultural habitus or the high economic costs related to outdoor practices. Many ethnic Norwegian residents, aware that they are the desired residents in the geopolitical strategy of maintaining Longyearbyen as a Norwegian family community, leverage their position by drawing on the rhetoric of "bolyst" (desire to dwell) as argument against environmental policy changes:

We want to see Svalbard and experience Svalbard... that's why we live here. Not necessarily because we want to maintain a Norwegian settlement here. [...] And if you want to maintain a Norwegian society here, where at least the basis is Norwegian, then I think you need to think twice before you restrict our freedom to roam here. *(Interview with male, long-term inhabitant of Svalbard, in his fifties, February 2020)*

Second, there are frictions between the experiential and economic dimensions: There is a tension between the opportunity and freedom to roam the empty landscape as an element valued as central to a good life on Svalbard on the one hand, and the economic importance of the wilderness as an exotic (and valuable) tourist destination for wealthy tourists on the other. Increasing infrastructural developments and tourism is believed to devalue the “outdoor experience” making it less adventurous:

It is a bit egoistic maybe, that I want to have [the Svalbard landscape] to myself. But I remember in the 90s, when we drove to the East Coast, when it was a bit more of an expedition that it is today, when we went to a cabin for a weekend, then we were all alone, and that is what we locals want on Svalbard, that is why we are here and why we go on trips. If you drive for example to Mohnbukta today, on a Saturday morning, then there are fifty scooters there with tourists, and that is not so charming.
(Interview with male Norwegian long-term resident of Svalbard, 54 years, May 2020)

As expressed in this quote, there is a sense that places that were once remote and empty are getting increasingly crowded. While this concern might be dismissed as nostalgia for an idealized past, it points to a deeper problematic: namely a fundamental shift in the way humans relate to the environment once the outdoor experience is commodified. The ability to engage with nature in a *resonant* (Rosa 2019) and meaningful way is reduced when nature becomes a product to be consumed and tourism potentially transform human engagements with nature from experiential to commodified and instrumental relations.

Furthermore, the increased environmental protection and regulations on Svalbard are partly emerging in response to the impact produced by tourism. Thus, there is an indirect causal connection between the expansion of tourism and the reduced accessibility and opportunities to engage with nature through in non-commercial settings. This raises a fundamentally political question of whether the Svalbardian wilderness should only be available to the people who can afford to participate in a guided excursion? Svalbard is not unique in this regard, but part of a larger international trend where natural areas are increasingly subject to environmental restrictions and access fees, effectively privatizing the natural landscape.

Third, the economic dimension enters in conflict with the political when environmental protection and regulations limits segments of the tourist industry’s opportunity to commercialize the Svalbard landscape. While the tourist industry sells experiences of the

Svalbard wilderness, environmental authorities see the need to protect the environment from increased human pressure. However, this tension is not evenly distributed among commercial actors. Rather, it favors some actors above others. The proposed regulations will concentrate tourist traffic in certain areas, making it harder to sell experiences *off the beaten track*. Paradoxically, the Norwegian state pointed out tourism as a main economic pillar on Svalbard already when transitioning from the mono-industrial company-town model, and again in the current envisioned transition from coal extraction into a sustainable future (Hovelsrud et. al 2021). From a local perspective, the mixed signals from the state, encouraging tourism on the one hand and restricting its access to the environment on the other, lead to confusion and frustration. The relationship between the tourist industry and the Norwegian environmental authorities, including the environmental office at the Governor of Svalbard, has thus become an uneasy one, where tourist operators often feel that regulations choke their businesses.

Photo: Tomas Salem

5. Conclusions and reflections

Access to nature and outdoor activities are important factors of wellbeing and constitutive of what is considered the good life on Svalbard. In addition to experiential and cultural values, the Svalbard landscape is also source to commercial and political values, which results in various tensions between these different dimensions. As the wilderness is being encroached by tourism and curtailed by environmental policies, state and market in combination threaten locals' experiential relations to the environment.

In the description of the tension between different perspectives and uses of Svalbard's landscape, we thus observe the complexity and negotiations of an ongoing territorial reordering of space. Tourism appears as both a problem and solution, residents resist changes brought on by the tourist industry but align with local tour operators to resist the state, and the state acts as both a facilitator of continued growth in tourism and as a regulator imposing conditions and seeking to protect the intangible values of the Svalbardian wilderness. These complexities are the result of negotiations between the capitalist imperative of growth and the negative effects of continued economic expansion and growth on local communities, ecosystems, and ways of life.

Nature conservation research has shown that "conflict is often at the heart of protected-area establishment and maintenance" partly due to "clumsy top-down approaches by states that fail to appreciate, or work with, local practices and interests" (West et al. 2006: 260). One way of tempering the current conflict over environmental regulations and regaining trust in environmental authorities would thus be to involve the inhabitants of in the development of new legal frameworks and the establishment of protected areas. As was pointed out several times in the interviews, another possible way to alleviate the tensions would be to nuance and assess the relative environmental impact of different actors and activities. On the one hand, many locals argue that their impact is limited, as they are limited in number and only a few travel far. On the other hand, the environmental impact of small-scale tourist operators cannot be compared to that of large-scale actors such as Hurtigruten or Svalbard Adventures.

Importantly, the dilemmas that we have laid out in this report are local expressions of structural tensions that have emerged in the last decades, as "environmental concerns" have

increasingly become a part of the public agenda, while faith in modernity's promise of progress has declined. There seems to be a growing consensus that we are at an impasse, and diverging opinions on how to solve the challenges presented by a socioeconomic model premised on continued growth in a finite world. The question of our time, which we see reflected in debates about the good life on Svalbard, is how to balance environmental, economic, and social concerns (i.e. questions of social justice). A recurring critique towards perspectives drawing on the notion of the Anthropocene is that they tend to be depoliticizing as they establish the primacy of nature as *the* concern that must be addressed at all costs. Thus, the environmental argument in an authoritative argument that often conceals the political and economic dynamics underpinning the problem. When issues of social justice, democratic participation, or equality are discussed, these are often understood as secondary concerns in relation to the imperative to protect the environment. What remains unchallenged in these debates is the socioeconomic system that produces "the problem" in the first place. It is our hope that by documenting cultural practices and meanings attributed to the Svalbardian landscape and showing how these are central to collective identities and ways of life, we can lift the debate on the future of Svalbard from the technocratic sphere, concerned with administrating "the environment" and into the political realm, where the questions of what kind of world we want to create and what kind of lives we want to live are brought to the fore.

6. Dissemination activities

In May 2021 we were accompanied by documentary filmmaker Siri Bråtveit. She is still accompanying the research process and her documentary does not have a release date yet. In May 2022, we presented our preliminary findings at the public library in Longyearbyen in combination with a photographic exposition. The public lecture was visited by 20 people who engaged in a discussion around our project and findings after the presentation. We are currently in the final stages of an article that will be submitted to an international peer-reviewed journal. Pictures from fieldwork were also exposed at *2Walls Studio* in Barcelona in December 2021 and presented the research in the *Nordic Laboratory* seminar series at the University of Oslo in June 2022, as well as in an international workshop at the University of Bergen in June 2022. Furthermore, we have presented findings in a public talk at *Conversas*

Barcelona in October 2022. The research will be included in Tomas Salem's doctoral dissertation at the University of Bergen, due in August 2024. We are currently working on a photo-essay for the workshop [Decolonize Nordic Nature](#) and the edited volume that will result from the workshop. In this essay we will further explore the phenomenological and experiential dimensions of *friluftsliv* on Svalbard and connect them to a theoretical critique of the distinction between western and non-western cosmologies. In September 2020 we were invited to the high school in Longyearbyen to discuss our research and methods with students in the school's Anthropology course. In May 2021 we organized an excursion to the beach with the high school students coursing *friluftsliv*, where we presented our project and discussed the student's understanding of the topics we cover.

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